
Material Continuity in Ceramic Restoration: A Firing-Based Protocol Integrating Digital Technologies

Reintegration with Materials Identical to the Original Object and Ceramic 3D Technology

Case Study: Buddha-Shaped Tureen, 18th century — Caramulo Museum

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Abstract

This paper documents the development and application of a ceramic restoration protocol based on reintegration using materials identical to the original object — paste and glazes fired at high temperature — in Chinese export porcelain. The protocol addresses the problem of material incoherence between the original object and its reconstruction, ensuring compatibility of thermal behaviour and equivalent durability, which are unachievable with conventional synthetic materials.

The case study focuses on the complete reconstruction of the lid of a Chinese export porcelain tureen belonging to the Caramulo Museum. The intervention, carried out between 2019 and 2023, involved the selection and characterisation of compatible ceramic pastes, glaze matching, dimensional modelling compensating for the shrinkage coefficient (16.8%), and the integration of 3D scanning and ceramic 3D printing to resolve complex lid-fitting geometry.

Through an interrupted firing protocol at defined temperature thresholds — 150°C, 350°C and 573°C — the alpha→beta quartz transformation was identified as the critical moment of crack formation. The solution involved separating the functions of the firing support and firing the components independently, eliminating the internal stresses responsible for the cracking. The process required 20 iterations over four years, resulting in a porcelain lid delivered to the Caramulo Museum in September 2023.

The protocol is not a universal solution: its application is conditioned by the scale of the intervention, the technical feasibility of execution in compatible ceramic systems, and the conditions of firing process control. Reconstructed elements are marked with the author's signature and year of execution, ensuring permanent traceability.

Keywords: ceramic restoration; Chinese export porcelain; material continuity; high-firing restoration; ceramic 3D printing; firing protocol; heritage conservation

1. Introduction

This paper describes the development and application of a ceramic restoration method based on reintegration using materials identical to the original object — ceramic paste and glazes fired at high temperature. The central problem this method addresses is the material incoherence between the original object and its reconstruction: by using the same ceramic materials as the original, compatibility of thermal behaviour and equivalent durability are achieved — results impossible to attain with conventional synthetic materials. Aesthetic fidelity — matching glazes, decoration and ageing patina — is a direct consequence of this material compatibility.

The method was developed autonomously over fifteen years and applied professionally to Chinese export porcelain from reference museum and private collections, covering situations of partial loss and total structural loss of constituent elements.

The term *high-firing restoration* designates an approach to reintegration based on the use of ceramic paste compatible with the original material, fired at high temperature, establishing material continuity between the original part and the reintegrated part. This approach has documented use in Portuguese conservation practice in the field of tile conservation, where it designates the ceramic production of missing fragments for reintegration, as opposed to cold restoration using synthetic materials [1]. This paper applies the same principle to Chinese export porcelain, in a context distinguished by the specificity of the material, the scale of interventions, and the integration of ceramic 3D technology.

Ceramic reintegration with fired elements has historical precedents documented since the eighteenth century, particularly in the replacement of missing lids and parts from Asian porcelain with faience or ceramic materials distinct from the original [4]. This practice was, however, technically limited: porcelain can shrink between 15% and 17% during firing, and each additional firing increases the risk of fracture and distortion [4]. The protocol documented here systematically resolves these technical difficulties and goes beyond historical practice: it does not use a distinct ceramic material, but material identical to the original — paste and glazes of the same technical family as the object being restored.

Recent research documents the use of ceramic 3D printing in the restoration of historic porcelain, identifying the plastic materials conventionally used as problematic due to their chromatic instability over time, and proposing that replacement of damaged areas be carried out using material specific to the type [2]. The present case study develops this direction into a complete protocol: 3D technology is integrated as an instrument of geometric precision within a process whose reintegration is executed in real porcelain, fired at high temperature, using the same materials as the original object. To the best of the author's knowledge, no public documentation exists of a protocol with this degree of specificity applied to Chinese export porcelain.

The case study presented is the restoration of a Buddha-shaped tureen in Chinese export porcelain with famille rose enamels, belonging to the Caramulo Museum, with intervention carried out between 2019 and 2023.

2. Definition and Principles of High-Firing Restoration

High-firing restoration designates a reintegration approach in ceramic restoration based on the use of ceramic paste compatible with the original material, fired at high temperature, establishing material continuity between the original part and the reintegrated part. The designation distinguishes itself from cold restoration, which uses synthetic materials such as resins and filling pastes [1]. This paper applies this principle to Chinese export porcelain, with technical specificities determined by the nature of the material and the scale of the interventions.

Fundamental principles

- **Material continuity:** reintegration is carried out using materials identical to the original — paste and glazes of the same technical family as the object — and not merely generic ceramic material. This distinguishes the approach from historically documented practices of substitution with a distinct ceramic material, such as faience replacing porcelain [4].
- **Physico-chemical compatibility:** the materials used present affinity with the original ceramic body in terms of composition, thermal behaviour and ageing response.
- **Behavioural coherence:** the intervention seeks to ensure that the whole — original and reintegrated — presents a consistent response over time.
- **Restitution of object unity:** reintegration aims to restore the formal, structural and, where applicable, functional legibility of the object as a coherent whole.
- **Evidence-based intervention:** reconstruction is grounded in material evidence, comparative documentation or formal analysis, avoiding free reconstructions.
- **Reversibility and integrity of the original:** reintegrated elements are never fused with or incorporated into the original ceramic body. Their attachment to the object is achieved by bonding using conventional restoration techniques, keeping the reintegrated elements removable without damage to the original. The original object is never altered by the intervention process.
- **Transparency and identification of the intervention:** reconstructed elements are marked with the author's own signature and year of execution, ensuring permanent distinction between original and reintegration and guaranteeing future traceability of the intervention.

Scope and limits of application

High-firing restoration applies to situations of partial loss and total structural loss of constituent elements. It is particularly appropriate when differences in material behaviour may compromise the long-term durability of the intervention, or when the loss of elements with structural or load-bearing function renders conventional solutions insufficient. It is not a universal approach: it is inadvisable for small-scale interventions where conventional solutions are sufficient, and in situations where there is insufficient basis for a grounded reconstruction. The process requires specialised technical expertise in ceramics and thermal processes, rigorous control of variables, and capacity for experimental iteration.

3. Case Study Background

The Buddha-shaped tureen in Chinese export porcelain with famille rose enamels, belonging to the Caramulo Museum, is an object of singular heritage significance. Few examples of this figurative typology are known, and its place within the museum collection imposed heightened demands of formal and material rigour on the intervention.

At the time of the intervention, the tureen was on display with a faience lid, materially and formally incompatible with the original object. The faience piece did not respect the iconographic configuration of the ensemble — it represented a generic oriental figure with no correspondence to the Buddha figure — showed clear signs of wear with glaze detachment and multiple repaired fractures, and resulted from a reconstruction with no basis in historical or comparative documentation. The situation compromised the material coherence, formal legibility and typological integrity of the ensemble.

The proposed intervention consisted of producing a new lid in porcelain, materially compatible with the original, based on comparative references from examples of the same period and typology. For this purpose, photographic records of similar tureens were analysed and, where possible, measurements were collected from original pieces temporarily accessible.

4. Development of the Intervention

The work was carried out between November 2019 and September 2023, structured in sequential phases determined by the nature of the problems encountered. The following table summarises the experimental chronology of the 20 iterations performed.

Phase	Date	Problem	Approach	Outcome
1–4	2020–21	Incorrect curvature; cracks in lid	Manual modelling; firing supports	Curvature unresolved; cracks persist
5–8	2022	Fitting geometry not reproducible manually	3D scanning (EinScan-SP); reverse engineering (Solid Edge); ceramic 3D printing (Delta Wasp)	Curvature and dimension resolved; cracks persist
9–12	2022–23	Origin of cracks undetermined	Interrupted firings 150°C / 350°C / 573°C	Cause identified: restraint to contraction at phase transformation
13–16	2023	Rigid support generates stress at phase transformation	Independent supports; separate firing of lid/head	Final lid crack-free; precise fit
Total	2019–23		16 complete pieces + 4 bases	Delivery: 28/09/2023

Table 1 — Experimental chronology (2019–2023).

4.1 Material selection and resizing

In 2020, following survey of the tureen at the Caramulo Museum, the paste was selected and measurements studied for resizing. The paste initially selected was extruded Artica porcelain paste (plastic route), with moisture content between 18% and 23%, suited to manual modelling by its plasticity and consistency. The shrinkage coefficient during firing at 1280°C is 16.8%, determining that any element to be reproduced must be modelled proportionally larger than the original — which precludes direct reproduction by mould from an original piece.

In parallel, atomised Artica paste (liquid route) was tested, presented as granulated powder with residual moisture between 4% and 7%, prepared in suspension with water and deflocculants for slip casting. Atomised paste is more fluid and less prone to retaining modelling stresses. The shrinkage coefficient of the atomised version is slightly lower, approximately 15.4% at 1280°C. Both pastes were used and tested throughout the process, with and without 3D printing integration. The central problem — cracking — proved independent of the paste used, being determined by the behaviour of the firing support, as documented in sections 4.6 and 4.7. The lid delivered to the Caramulo Museum was executed in extruded paste, with a shrinkage coefficient of 16.8%.

Reference measurements were collected from a Chinese export porcelain tureen lid, dating to the Qianlong period, temporarily available in Lisbon at Jorge Welsh Works of Art, and supplemented by the analysis of comparative photographic documentation of examples from the same period and typology.

Fig. 7 – Reference lid, Jorge Welsh Works of Art

Fig. 8 – Measuring the reference lid

Fig. 9 – Comparative photographic analysis for resizing

4.2 Fitting geometry and development of the firing support

A specific challenge of this tureen was that the fitting rim of the lid presented an asymmetric inclination — simulating the shoulders and chest of the figure — rather than a flat rim as is usual. This geometry required high-precision reproduction: small variations in the angle of curvature after firing resulted in misalignment and instability in the seating of the lid.

The mass distribution of the lid — with the sculptural head positioned in the central area — induced pressure on the base during firing, aggravating the fitting problems and increasing the potential for deformation. To control these variables, a specific support was developed with three simultaneous functions: to serve as a reference for dimension and angle during modelling; to support the piece during air drying; and to support the lid during firing. The support proved essential in the first two functions — modelling reference and drying support — and continued to be used in these functions until the end of the process. It was precisely its presence during firing that was subsequently identified as the cause of the cracks: the restraint it imposed on the natural contraction of the porcelain at the moment of phase transformation generated internal stresses that manifested as cracks. The solution involved separating the functions — the support was retained for modelling and drying, but replaced by independent props during firing.

Fig. 10 – Fitting rim with asymmetric inclination

Fig. 11 – Modelling, drying and firing support

4.3 Glaze matching

In parallel with formal development, glaze matching tests were initiated in 2020. The glazes used were O-6025 and O-6048 (Vicente Diaz), complemented with ceramic stains (iron red, black, dark red) and engobes (P7, E.56, E.59). The process involved producing series of fired samples for iterative adjustment of colour, translucency and gloss, with the aim of matching the original glazes of the piece.

4.4 Modelling and plaster moulds

In 2021, modelling of the lid and support was initiated. The model was separated into distinct parts — lid, head, ears and support — for the production of plaster moulds of each component. The dimension of the model before firing is significantly larger than the original, reflecting the calculated shrinkage coefficient. Upon completion, the model was presented to the client for approval.

Fig. 18 – Modelling of firing support

Fig. 19 – Lid and support model for plaster mould production

Fig. 20 – Detail of oversizing of modelled piece

Fig. 21 – Plaster moulds

4.5 Integration of 3D scanning and ceramic 3D printing

The first lids produced by slip casting presented, after firing, incorrect curvature and crack formation. Resolution by exclusively manual means proved insufficient given the asymmetric geometry of the tureen's rim.

Fig. 22 – First lids being fired

Fig. 23 – Lid with incorrect angle

Fig. 24 – Appearance of cracks in lid

In January 2022, three-dimensional scanning of the tureen was carried out using the EinScan-SP scanner (Shining 3D). The scanned image was processed through reverse engineering with Solid Edge 2021, generating an STL model adjusted to the shrinkage percentage of the paste — compensating the 16.8% shrinkage coefficient directly in the digital geometry. The model was prepared for printing with Simplify 3D and printed on a Delta Wasp 2040 Pro ceramic printer. The printed base reproduced with precision the geometry of the tureen's rim, providing a reliable geometric reference for the new lid mould. This integration resolved the curvature and fitting dimension problems [3].

The introduction of ceramic 3D printing does not replace the ceramic process — which remains the core of the method — but resolves a specific problem of geometric precision that manual reproduction could not guarantee with this morphology.

4.6 Crack diagnosis — interrupted firing protocol

Despite the resolution of the geometry problems, cracking persisted. The diagnostic approach adopted was the execution of interrupted firings in phases, with the objective of identifying the exact moment of crack formation throughout the thermal cycle. Two lids were fired simultaneously: one complete lid with firing support; and one lid without head and without support.

- **150°C** — loss of all constitutional water. Result: no cracks.
- **350°C** — combustion of organic matter in the paste. Result: no cracks.
- **573°C** — alpha→beta quartz transformation, with exponential volume increase. Result: complete lid with support showed cracks; lid without support intact.

The identified cause: the firing support, with thermal behaviour distinct from the lid, restrained the natural expansion/contraction of the porcelain at the moment of phase transformation at 573°C, generating internal stresses that manifested as cracks. The solution involved redefining the support system: independent props were developed to provide the necessary geometric support without impeding the natural movement of the piece. It was additionally decided to fire the lid and the head separately in the first firing (bisque firing), joining them only at the glaze application stage in the second firing. This solution eliminated the cracking.

4.7 Firing protocol

The firing cycle adopted followed the standard bi-firing protocol for porcelain, with a third firing determined by the specific requirements of this intervention:

- **First firing — bisque firing at 980°C**, in an oxidising atmosphere. Confers mechanical strength to the unfired piece and eliminates residual organic compounds from the paste, preparing the surface for glaze application.
- **Second firing — vitrification and glazing at 1275°C**. The paste reaches full vitrification and the glaze melts and adheres permanently. Carried out with independent props.
- **Third firing — glaze correction at 1275°C**. Required to glaze the inner support area of the head after its removal, ensuring complete coverage.

The control of the firing curve — rate of temperature increase, safety plateaux and cooling — was decisive for the stability of the piece, particularly in the phase transformation zone identified in the diagnostic protocol.

5. Results

In July 2023 the first complete lid with final decoration was completed. During a subsequent correction to the decoration, the piece developed a crack in the kiln, making delivery impossible. A second lid was produced, completed in September 2023 and delivered to the Caramulo Museum on 28 September 2023.

Over the course of the process, between 2019 and 2023, **16 complete pieces** were produced with their respective supports and props, and four lids (base only), totalling twenty iterations that document the experimental progression of the method.

6. Conclusion

This case study documents the application of a ceramic restoration protocol with material continuity, developed through practice and in response to concrete problems. The articulation between material knowledge, process control and digital tools made it possible to develop solutions for situations of greater complexity, particularly in contexts of extensive loss with structural requirements. The intervention demonstrated the viability of reintegration using materials identical to the original object — ceramic paste and glazes fired at high temperature — with compatibility of thermal behaviour and durability equivalent to the original.

The integration of 3D scanning and ceramic 3D printing does not replace the ceramic process, but resolves with precision the problems of dimension and fitting geometry in pieces with complex morphology. The use of the EinScan-SP scanner, processed through reverse engineering with Solid Edge and printed on the Delta Wasp 2040 Pro, made it possible to compensate for the shrinkage coefficient directly in the digital model. It is this specific articulation — digital geometric precision

combined with material reintegration in real porcelain — that distinguishes the protocol from existing literature, which documents the use of 3D in ceramic restoration exclusively with synthetic materials [2].

The analysis of firing behaviour and the identification of the conditions of crack formation — namely the alpha→beta quartz transformation at 573°C as the critical moment of stress — contributed to the definition of a technically grounded protocol, applicable and adaptable to cases with similar material and formal characteristics.

The method is part of a fifteen-year practice applied to diverse situations — partial and total losses — in Chinese export porcelain. Its applicability is selective: it is intended for objects of high heritage value where conventional solutions would compromise material or aesthetic integrity in the long term, and requires specific technical conditions — kiln, scanning equipment, ceramic printer, command of thermal processes. It is not presented as a universal solution, its application being dependent on the scale of the intervention, the technical feasibility of execution in compatible ceramic systems, and the conditions of firing process control.

The Jingdezhen Imperial Kiln Institute has recently developed three innovative restoration approaches, including porcelain-to-porcelain restoration, applied primarily to archaeological fragments of imperial production pieces using AI for pattern assembly and reconstruction. The present work operates in a distinct field: elite export porcelain in a European context, with partial or total losses of constituent elements, and with a documented high-temperature firing protocol for physical reintegration. To the best of the author's knowledge, no public documentation exists of a complete protocol with this degree of specificity for this context.

The approach further integrates principles of transparency and identification of reintegrations: reconstructed elements are marked with the author's own identification and year of execution, ensuring permanent distinction between original and intervention and future traceability.

References

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Annex I — Materials and Equipment

Ceramic materials

- Artica Extruded Porcelain — plastic route; manual modelling; shrinkage 16.8% at 1280°C
- Artica Atomised Porcelain — liquid route; slip casting; shrinkage ~15.4% at 1280°C
- Plaster (moulds)
- Glaze O-6025 Vicente Diaz / Glaze O-6048 Vicente Diaz
- Ceramic stains: iron red, black, dark red
- Engobes: P7, E.56, E.59

3D scanning and printing equipment

- EinScan-SP (Shining 3D) — three-dimensional scanning
- Solid Edge 2021 — modelling and reverse engineering
- Simplify 3D — slicing software
- Delta Wasp 2040 Pro — ceramic 3D printer

Photographic equipment

- Nikon Z50 / Nikkor Z 50mm f/1.8 S
- Capture One

Annex II — Photographic Gallery

Photographic record of the process in chronological order. Annex II is intended to complement the photographic record in the main body of the text with additional images documenting intermediate stages or complementary angles.

Tureen with faience lid, Caramulo Museum

Buddha-shaped tureen, Chinese export porcelain, Qianlong late 18th century, Royal Collection Trust

Buddha-shaped tureen, Chinese export porcelain, Qianlong 1736–1795, Berta Berg Collection

Reference model, Jorge Welsh Works of Art

Detail of interior of reference lid

Detail of face of reference lid

Colour studies

Face modelling

Face modelling (cont.)

Completion of lid and support modelling

First firing (bisque firing)

Glazing

First lids — cracks and incorrect angle

First lids — cracks and incorrect angle

First lids — cracks and incorrect angle

Detail of cracks

Detail of cracks

Detail of cracks

Detail of tureen rim curvature

3D scanning of tureen rim

Reverse engineering for firing support production

Reverse engineering for firing support production

Printing of new firing support

Printing of new firing support

Support assembly after printing

Assembled support after printing

New modelled lid

New lid fitted to printed support

Drying process

Drying process in oven

Drying process in oven

First crack-free lid

Detail of first crack-free lid

Detail of first crack-free lid

First decorations

Finalisation of decoration

Final lid

Final lid

Final lid

Firing supports and 4 lids without head

16 complete lids

Photographic recording

Photographic recording

Image processing

Image processing

*Buddha tureen on display at
Caramulo Museum*

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